

THE
CAPONIIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA

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THE CAPONIIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The family Caponiidae is a small family with 18 genera and 119 species known from North and South America and Africa. In Southern Africa. A total of 16 species of the Caponiidae is known from South Africa represented by two genera. The genus *Diplogena* (6 spp.) was recently revised by Haddad (2015) but *Caponia* (10 spp.) is still not revised. Of the 582 specimens presently housed in the National Collection of Arachnida around 25 % are identified to species level. For *Caponia*, five species are listed as Least Concern and five are data deficient known only from one sex. For *Diplogena* four species is least concern with one, *Diplogena dippenaarae* Haddad, 2015, regarded as Endangered and *D. proxila* Haddad, 2015 Critical Rare.

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Caponia hastifera female from Fouriesburg Photo Peter Webb

FAMILY CAPONIIDAE Simon, 1890

The Caponiidae is a small family described by Simon (1890) with 18 genera and 119 species known from North and South America and Africa. In South Africa they are represented by two genera and 16 species in the Atlas Region (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Orange Lungless Spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Medium-sized (6-13 mm). Colour: Their carapace and legs are orange-yellow, with only a dark spot over the eye region; the abdomen is a uniform silky grey. Carapace oval, anteriorly narrower, lacking a distinct fovea and striation; integument is smooth and shiny; eyes two (*Diploglena*) or eight (*Caponia*). Abdomen elongate oval with a light covering of dark setae; booklungs replaced by two pairs of tracheae; epigastric region and tracheae often with chitinous strip; spinnerets modified with median spinnerets situated between anterior spinnerets. Legs three-clawed, short, sturdy and without spines; coxae and often the patellae of leg I are much longer than the rest; tarsi with trichobothria legs fold over the body when at rest. Genitalia: haplogyne; female with copulatory opening concealed beneath integument; spermathecae paired but reduced; male palp with well-developed tarsus; bulbus simple, inserted in small alveolus; embolus varies from a short spiniform process (*Diploglena*) to extremely long and curved with a bifurcated tip (*Caponia*).

LIFE STYLE: Caponiids are usually found on the ground under stones or in leaf litter. Very little is known about their behaviour. They are nocturnal spiders and swift runners pursuing their prey over the ground. During the day they are found in saclike retreats under stones or other ground debris. They build a small oval retreat of transparent silk which they attach to stones and ground debris. *Caponia* was frequently collected in Southern Africa from areas infested with harvester termites (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014).

TAXONOMY: Only *Diploglena* was recently revised (Haddad 2015).

Caponiidae. a: *Caponia* sp., female, dorsal view; b: *Diploglena* eye pattern, dorsal view; c: *Caponia* sp., eye pattern, dorsal view; d: mouthparts; e: abdomen, ventral view, showing tracheal spiracles; f: spinnerets, ventral view. g: male palp, lateral view. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997).

GENUS *CAPONIA* Simon, 1887

The genus *Caponia* described by Simon (1887) is an African endemic represented by 10 species of which nine are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Eight-eyed Orange Lungless Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Caponia natalensis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1874)

DIAGNOSTIC CHARACTERS: Orange lungless spiders are small to medium-sized spiders recognised by the orange-yellow carapace and legs, with only a dark spot over the eye region. Carapace oval, attenuated anteriorly; lacking a distinct fovea and striation; clypeus broad and sloping, sometimes porrect; eight eyes arranged in compact group around anterior median eyes. Sternum oval and more or less elongated and flat with a sinuous edge; labium separated from sternum by a shallow depression. Abdomen oval with sparse covering of dark setae; epigastric region and tracheae often with chitinous strip. Legs three claws; legs short and sturdy with coxae and often patellae of leg I much longer than in other legs (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997).

LIFE STYLE: Caponiids are usually found on the ground under stones or in leaf litter. They are swift runners, pursuing their prey on the ground. Their small oval retreats of transparent silk are attached to stones and debris. Although rare, they are widely distributed in the Afrotropical Region. Lawrence (1964) considered them to be inhabitants of arid or desert regions, but pitfall trap surveys in South Africa have shown that they also occur in pine plantations and forested areas (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1988; Van der Merwe, 1994). Little is known about their feeding behaviour but according to Platnick (1993), anecdotal information suggests that they prey on spiders. *Caponia* has been frequently collected in South Africa in areas infested with harvester termites (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991). In the laboratory, termites are readily accepted as prey.

TAXONOMY: The genus is in need of a revision.

Caponia sp. male Photo: P. Webb

Caponia sp. female Photo: P. Webb

Caponia braunsi Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Braun's Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Willowmore. It is known from two provinces (EEO=4 250 km²; AOO=24 km²; 367-931 m a.s.l.). The two collections in the Eastern Cape were made before 1904, but the collections in the Western Cape, from two protected areas, are more recent. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: Free-living ground dwellers that are typically found on the ground surface. They are active at night and swift runners that pursue their prey over the ground. They usually rest during the day in a small oval retreat built of transparent silk, stones and ground debris that is constructed under rocks, soil debris or in grass tussocks.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Alicedale (-33.31, 26.08); Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). *Western Cape:* Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.36, 21.69); Witteberg Nature Reserve (-33.3442, 20.5052); Laingsburg, Floriskraal Dam (-33.2937, 20.9927); Laingsburg (-33.20, 20.85).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020), Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and Witteberg Nature Reserve. But some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range..

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male.

Male palp after Purcell (1904).

Caponia braunsi Addo Elephant National Park Photo: Linda Wiese

Caponia capensis Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Cape Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Purcell (1904), from the Table Mountain National Park in South Africa. The species is known also from Namibia and Mozambique. In South Africa it is known from three provinces (EOO=236 641 km²; AOO=68 km²; 7-1172 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range and the lack of significant threats it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free-living ground dwellers that wander around on the ground surface. They are active at night and swift runners that pursue their prey over the ground. They are frequently sampled in pitfall traps from the Grassland and Fynbos biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5); Alicedale (-33.31, 26.08). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 24.82). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Mamre (-33.5, 18.45); St. Helena Bay (-32.77, 18.03); Table Mountain National Park (Devils Peak) (-33.91, 18.42); Malmesbury (-33.46, 18.74); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB 7.3, 1179 m a.s.l. (-32.46, 19.24); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg 2.4, 251 m a.s.l. (-32.28, 18.53); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Driehoek 6.2, 919 m a.s.l. (-32.42, 18.16); Cederberg Wilderness Area Sawadee CIB 3.4, 332 m a.s.l. (-32.34, 18.99); Cederberg Wilderness Area Niewoudt's Pass, CIB 4.3, 551 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.01); Cederberg Wilderness Area Wupperthal, CIB 17.1, 522 m a.s.l. (-32.28, 19.22); Knysna (-34.03, 23.03); Robben Island (-33.8, 18.35); St. Helena Bay Stompneus (-32.77, 18.03).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009); Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016); Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020e) and Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020b). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Caponia capensis female from de Hoop NR Photo Charles Haddad

Male palp after Purcell (1904).

Caponia capensis male and female genitalia from Cederberg Wilderness Area Photo ASD

Caponia chelifera Lessert, 1936

COMMON NAME: Mozambique Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lessert (1936), from Mozambique. The species is also known from Zimbabwe and South Africa. In South Africa, it is known from four provinces (EOO=106 988 km²; AOO=56 km²; 70-1 415 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free living ground dwellers. They are wandering spiders typically found on the ground surface. They are active at night and swift runners that pursue their prey over the ground. They usually rest during the day in a small oval retreat built of transparent silk, stones and ground debris that is constructed under rocks, soil debris or in grass tussocks. They are sometimes sampled in pitfall traps. Known from the Grasland, Forest and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria, Roodeplaat Nature Reserve (-25.63, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Mkuzi Game Reserve) (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Luvhondo Nature Reserve, (-23.03, 29.45); Malebogo Nature Reserve (-23.07, 28.88); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Springbok Flats: Wildskamp (-24.49, 28.46), Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46), Roedtan (-24.6, 29.08), Bekendevelei (-24.52, 28.51); Legalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25); Roedtan, Springbokvlakte (-24.6, 29.08); Vhembe Biosphere, Goro Game Ranch (-22.959, 29.421). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg Farm Sterkfontein 521T, Booyensdal (-25.09, 30.46); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in nine protected areas such as Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Mueelwa et al. 2010); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008) and Legalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Caponia chelifera female and male Photo ASD

Caponia chelifera male palp Photo ASD

Male palp after Purcell (1904).

Caponia forcifera Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Forest Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape Province endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Brandvlei. The species is known from three old collections: Knysna (1896), Brandvlei, Worcester (1900) and Swellendam (around 1900) (EOO=5 482 km²; AOO=16 km²; 120-566 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Forest Biome but specific habitat for this species is unknown.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Worcester, Brandvlei (-33.64, 19.47); Knysna (-34.03, 23.03); Swellendam (Avontuur pass) (-33.72, 23.16); Swellendam (-34.02, 20.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Knysna Forest. More sampling needed to collect the female and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from males.

Caponia forcifera Photo: Z. van Dyk

Male palp after Purcell (1904).

Caponia hastifera Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Willowmore Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Willowmore. Known from two provinces (EOO=149 939 km²; AOO=36 km²; 17-1645 m a.s.l.) and recorded from three protected areas. Due to its wide geographical range and the fact that it is likely to be under collected, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller frequently sampled in pitfall traps. Sampled from the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Dunbrody (-33.47, 25.55); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5); Uitenhage (-33.76, 25.39); Andries Vosloo Kudu Reserve (-33.106, 26.776). *Free State:* Ficksburg (-28.86, 27.86); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.598, 26.430); Ficksburg (-28.875, 27.868); Wyndford Guest Farm, Fouriesburg (-28.7, 28.24); Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51, 25.25).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the following reserves: Andries Vosloo Kudu Reserve, Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018) and Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve. The species is threatened by loss of habitat infrastructure development in Port Elizabeth and Ficksburg and crop farming around Dunbrody.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Male palp illustrated.

Male palp after Purcell (1904).

Caponia hastifera female and male from Fourieburg
Photo Peter Webb

Caponia hastifera female Photo Charles Haddad

Caponia karrooica Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Karroo Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Matjiesfontein. The species is also known from Willowmore, where it was also recorded prior to 1904. The Campherskloof sample is a more recent collection (EOO=6 811 km²; EOO=12 km²; 850-912 m a.s.l.). It is likely to be under collected and the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Nama Karoo biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5). *Western Cape:* Worcester (-33.64, 19.47). Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); Campherskloof (-33.744, 23.002).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, only males known.

Male palp after Purcell (1904).

Caponia karrooica Photo: E. vd Westhuizen

Caponia natalensis (O.P.-Cambridge, 1874)

COMMON NAME: Natal Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by O.P.-Cambridge (1874) as *Colophon natalensis* with type locality only as Natal. Known from both sexes and sampled from four African countries. The species is from three provinces in South Africa. It is abundant in the Kruger National Park, with >20 records reported. It is also recorded from uMkhuze Game Reserve (EOO=18 147 km²; AOO=44 km²; 83-389 m a.s.l.). There are no recorded threats to the species, and considering its broad geographical range in Africa the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller frequently sampled in pitfall traps from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Namibia, Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52). *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Mkuze Game (-27.63, 32.25). *Limpopo:* Kruger National Park (Shingwedzi Camp) (-23.12, 31.43); Buzzard Mountain, Soutpansberg (-23.028, 29.767). *Mpumalanga:* Kruger National Park: Lwakahle (-25.38, 31.72), Makhuthwanini(-25.38, 31.6), Napi (-25.37, 31.51), Randspruit (-25.28, 31.64), Renosterkoppies (-25.14, 31.84), Satara (-24.38, 31.78), Sabiepoort 11 (-25.19, 32.2), Vutome (-25.24, 32.08).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Mkhuze Game Reserve, Ndumo Game Reserve, Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020c). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Caponia natalensis from Buzzard Mountain
Photo Dawn Toussaint

Male palp after Pickard-Cambridge (1874).

Caponia secunda Pocock, 1900

COMMON NAME: Thicket Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Pocock (1900) and known only from the type locality, in the Grahamstown area (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 565 m a.s.l.). There is not enough known about the habitat and range of this species for a full assessment to be conducted. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Thicket Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, only the female known.

Caponia secunda Photo: L. Wiese

Caponia simoni Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Simon's Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) and known only from the type locality Worcester, collected in 1896 (EOO=4 km²; EOO=4 km²; 428 m a.s.l.). Identification of the species is still problematic. More sampling is needed, to determine the species' range and a taxonomic revision is required. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for both data and taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed, to determine the species' range and a taxonomic revision is required.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, both sexes known.

Male palp after Purcell (1904).

Caponia spiralifera Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Hanover Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Hanover in the Northern Cape. The species has a wide distribution, recorded from five provinces (EOO=653 892 km²; AOO=36 km²; 56-1730 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Forest, Desert, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** East London (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.74, 28.19); Vereeniging (-26.67, 27.92); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.2). **Mpumalanga:** Bergvliet Forest Station (-25.1, 30.78). **North West:** Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22). **Northern Cape:** Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Namaqua National Park, Soebatsfontein (-30.11, 17.59).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the following areas: Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve, Bergvliet Forest Station, Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020), Namaqua National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020d) and Groenkloof Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Male palp after Purcell (1904).

Caponia spiralifera Photo: P. Webb

GENUS *DIPLOGLENA* Purcell, 1904

The genus *Diploglena* is known from six species (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: African Two-Eyed Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Diploglena capensis* Purcell, 1904

DIAGNOSTIC CHARACTERS: African two-eyed spiders are small to medium-sized spiders. They are recognised by the orange-yellow carapace and legs, with only a dark spot over the eye region covering the two eyes. The abdomen is uniformly silky grey. Their legs are the same colour as the carapace (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van den Berg 2010; Haddad 2015).

LIFE STYLE: They are rare nocturnal ground dwellers typically found on the ground surface mainly in the Northern and Western Cape provinces.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Haddad (2015).

Diploglena sp. Photo ASD

Eye pattern after Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997)

Diploglena arida Haddad, 2015

COMMON NAME: Corcordia Two-Eyed Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African species described by Haddad (2015), with the holotype male sampled 20 km N of Concordia in the Northern Cape. The species is known from several localities in the arid northern parts of the Northern Cape Province (EOO=8 686 km²; AOO=16 km²; 14-1048 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide range in southern Africa it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sometimes sampled in pitfall traps from the Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes. Two specimens were sampled from scorpion burrows (one individual from an *Opisthacanthus crassimanus* burrow).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Northern Cape: 20 km N of Concordia (-29.53, 17.94); Augrabies National Park (-28.66, 20.42); Kweekfontein (-29.483, 18.10); 13 km E of Port Nolloth (-29.25, 16.87)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Augrabies National Park (Dippenaar- Schoeman 2020a). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Diploglena arida female from Port Nolloth Photo Neville Cornberg

Male palp after Haddad (2015)

Diploglena capensis Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Cape Two-Eyed Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from St Helena Bay in Western Cape. The species is recorded only from a few localities and partly protected in the Cederberg Wilderness Area (EOO=8 km²; AOO=8 km²; 78-109 m a.s.l.). Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range, it is therefore listed as Data Deficient.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from humus in the Fynbos Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* St. Helena Bay (-32.77, 18.03); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Clanwilliam district (-32.16, 18.89)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Cederberg Wilderness area. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Haddad (2015). Known from both sexes.

Male palp after Haddad (2015)

Diploglena dippenaarae Haddad, 2015

COMMON NAME: Dippenaar's Two-Eyed Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: EN B1ab(ii,iii)+2ab(ii,iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Haddad (2015) from Jacobsbaai. The species is only known from two localities near Saldanha Bay (EOO= 8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 3-8 m a.s.l.) and appears to have a restricted distribution. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range. However a precautionary status of Endangered under criterion B is assigned due to high rates of habitat transformation taking place at the two known locations.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled at night from leaf litter in coastal Fynbos Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Jacobsbaai (-33.15 18.03); Saldanha (-33.01,17.93).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Male palp after Haddad (2015)

Diploglena karooca Haddad, 2015

COMMON NAME: Karoo Two-Eyed Orange Lungless Spiders

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Haddad (2015) from Tierberg, Prince Albert. The species is known from two provinces as well as from Namibia (EOO= 8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 834-1048 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range in southern Africa it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from pitfall traps, with one specimen sampled from a scorpion burrow in the Nama Karoo Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Concordia Henkies (-29.53, 17.94).

Western Cape: Prince Albert, Tierberg (-33.13 22.25).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Male palp after Haddad (2015)

Diploglena major Lawrence, 1928

COMMON NAME: Northern Two-Eyed Orange Lungless Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1928 as *Diploglena capensis major* from Namibia. The species has been sampled from western Namibia, eastern Botswana and the northern parts of South Africa. In South Africa it is known only from the Limpopo Province where it is protected in the Limpopo Valley National Park (EOO= 8 km²; AOO=8 km²; 531-605 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range in southern Africa it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled in pitfall traps from the Savanna Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Botswana and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Limpopo Valley (farm Stoke) (-22.492, 29.881)' Limpopo Valley National Park (-22.22, 29.13).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Limpopo Valley National Park. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Haddad (2015). Known from both sexes.

Diploglena major palp Photo: ASD

Male palp after Haddad (2015)

Diploglena proxila Haddad, 2015

COMMON NAME: Vredenburg Two-Eyed Orange Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: CR

NATIONAL CRITERIA: B1ab(ii,iii)+2ab(ii,iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Haddad (2015) from Vredenburg. The species is known only from the type locality (EOO= 4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 126 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range. However, a precautionary assessment of Critically Endangered under criterion B is assigned due to high levels of habitat transformation at the only known location.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled by hand from beneath rocks and plants in the Fynbos Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Vredenburg, Farm Besters Kraal 38. (-32.90, 17.99).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The only known population is threatened by loss of habitat to crop cultivation. The farm Bester's Kraal on the Vredenburg Peninsula where this species was collected has lost 80% of natural habitat to crop cultivation. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Male palp after Haddad (2015)

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